

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

Petar Bulat

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ŠTETNI EFEKTI ENDOKRINIH DISRUPTORA I NEIZVESNI REPRODUKTIVNI ISHODI

ENDOCRINE
DISRUPTORS

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Stalno interesovanje za izloženost životne sredine i reproduktivno zdravlje dovelo je do sve većeg broja studija koje se fokusiraju na endokrine disruptore (EDCs). Oni su deo našeg svakodnevnog života zbog njihove široke upotrebe. Na primer, plastifikatori, koji uključuju bisfenol A (BPA) i ftalate, prisutni su u hrani, ambalaži i potrošačkim proizvodima kao što su medicinski uređaji, kozmetika, farmaceutske proizvodi i igračke. Godišnja svetska proizvodnja plastike koja sadrži EDCs porasla je sa 50 miliona tona na 300 miliona tona od 1970-ih i još uvek raste.

Raniji pubertet kod devojčica, opadanje broja spermatozoida i genitalne malformacije otkriveni su širom sveta, što se danas najčešće povezuje sa izloženošću EDCs. Ove supstance se oslobađaju u životnu sredinu u nivoima koji možda ne predstavljaju značajne rizike, ali su efekti hronične izloženosti zabrinjavajući i mogu biti vrlo opasni. Povećani nivoi BPA i ftalata u urinu su povezani sa smanjenim brojem oocita, poremećenom folikulogenezom, pojavom fibroida i endometrioze kod žena. Takođe, pokazalo se da izlaganje BPA ugrožava implantaciju embriona, povećava rizik od sindroma policističnih jajnika i ponavljajućih pobačaja. Sa druge strane, smanjenje kvaliteta sperme, u smislu broja, zapremine i pokretljivosti sperme, kao i karcinom prostate zabeleženi su kod muškaraca izloženih BPA i ftalatima. Utvrđeno je da uobičajeni metaboliti ftalata izazivaju kriptorhizam, hipospadiju i sindrom disgeneze testisa, što dovodi do tumora testisa. Razumevanje efekata EDCs na reproduktivno zdravlje će pomoći u razvoju smernica i za pojedince i za industriju, i podstaknuti inovacije alternativnih jedinjenja koja ne utiču na plodnost i reproduktivno zdravlje, generalno.

KLJUČNE REČI: bisfenol A, ftalati, endokrini disruptor, reproduktivna toksikologija

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KLJUČNE REČI: bisfenol A, ftalati, endokrini ometači, reproduktivna toksičnost

UNCERTAIN REPRODUCTIVE OUTCOME AND DETRIMENTAL EFFECT OF ENDOCRINE- DISRUPTING CHEMICALS

ENDOCRINE
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Endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are now part of our daily life due to their widespread usage. For example, plasticizers, which include bisphenol A (BPA) and phthalates, are found in food, packaging, and consumer products such as medical devices, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and toys. Annual global production of plastics containing EDCs has increased from 50 to 300 million tons since the 1970s and it continues to grow. The risen earlier puberty in girls, the drop in sperm counts, and genital malformations have been found worldwide, which are linked now mainly to the EDCs exposure. These substances are released into the environment at levels that may not pose substantial risks, but the effects of chronic exposure are of concern and they can be in some way even deleterious.

The increased urinary BPA and phthalate concentrations have been associated with decreased oocyte yield, impaired folliculogenesis, fibroids, and endometriosis in women. In addition, BPA exposure has been shown to impair embryo implantation, increase the risk of polycystic ovary syndrome, and lead to repeated miscarriages. On the other hand, the deterioration of sperm quality, in terms of sperm count, volume and motility, as well as prostate cancer have been found in men exposed to both BPA and phthalates. Common phthalate metabolites were found to cause cryptorchidism, hypospadias, and testicular dysgenesis syndrome, leading to testicular cancer. Understanding the impact of EDCs on reproductive outcome will help developing the guidelines for both individuals and industry, and hopefully encourage innovations in alternative compounds that do not affect reproductive health.

KEYWORDS: bisphenol A, phthalates, endocrine disruptor, reproductive toxicology

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